

Programme d'Appui
à la mise en œuvre de l'Accord d'Association

Financé par l'Union européenne et géré par le Ministère du Commerce et de la
promotion des exportations

Proceedings of the International Congress

TEACHING

for

the

FUTURE

Appui au Ministère de
l'Enseignement Supérieur et de
la Recherche Scientifique pour le
renforcement des compétences
pédagogiques des enseignants
chercheurs et des capacités de
gouvernance des gestionnaires

Ministère de
l'Enseignement
Supérieur et de la
Recherche Scientifique

Junta de
Castilla y León

Diseño de cubierta y maquetación: Natalia Arnedo

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ISBN: 978-84-1369-354-5 • Depósito Legal: Gr. 964/2022

Impresión y encuadernación: COMARES

Summary

Il y a un art de savoir et un art d'enseigner.

CICERON

Ce Digibook est un ouvrage numérique collectif, consécutif au Congrès International organisé les 23 et 24 avril 2022, en mode hybride, en ligne et en présentiel à l'Université de la Formation continue d'Alger, par l'équipe de coordination d'un Programme d'Appui à la mise en œuvre de l'Accord d'Association Algérie-Union européenne (P3A) par l'intermédiaire d'un consortium d'universités espagnoles dirigé par l'Université de Valladolid, sous la direction de Pilar Garcès, Cheffe du projet PAPERS, partie Espagnole

Le slogan du Congrès, «*Teaching for the Future*» résume l'essence même du projet de jumelage intitulé «*Appui au Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche Scientifique pour le renforcement des compétences pédagogiques des enseignants chercheurs et des capacités de gouvernance des gestionnaires (PAPERS)*» entamé le 14 juillet 2019 et qui s'achèvera le 14 juillet 2022. Le projet s'est réalisé à travers l'organisation de 47 sessions de formations de 5 jours chacune, la mobilisation de 153 experts espagnols et la participation de 3.200 universitaires, tous profils confondus.

Ce Congrès avait pour but de présenter les résultats de ces trois années de cohabitation intellectuelle entre experts, enseignants, gestionnaire et ingénieurs, acteurs de la vie universitaire des deux rives de la Méditerranée, mus par le désir de partager le Savoir, ce bien immatériel à valeur universelle qui ne vaut que par l'usage qu'on en fait et ce Digibook en est la suite logique.

En effet, ce livre numérique constitue une contribution internationale et permet de faire le point sur les acquis du projet dans les trois volets qui le structurent:

- Volet 1: méthodologie universitaire
- Volet 2: formation de formateurs
- Volet 3: gouvernance universitaire.

Les contributions des 102 intervenants - en ligne et en présentiel- dénotent l'intérêt de la communauté universitaire internationale autour des interrogations sur les stratégies, les approches, les méthodes et les moyens d'ouvrir la voie à plus d'équité dans la recherche, la

répartition et l'usage de l'Economie de la Connaissance, dans le cadre d'un développement durable qui ouvre la perspective d'un monde moins clivant, donc plus juste.

Le partage des expériences pratiques et des réflexions théoriques consignées dans ce Digibook, laisse augurer de lendemains qui chantent sur tous les campus du monde, sans discrimination aucune, sans exclusive géographique ni économique.

Le projet Papers a généré une prise de conscience relative à la coopération universitaire, d'autant plus que le numérique est en train d'abattre les frontières physiques entre les pays. Dans le domaine de la Connaissance, le cercle vertueux commence par la recherche de la qualité, l'effort intellectuel, le sens de l'éthique, le respect de la propriété intellectuelle, l'ouverture sur l'universel, l'inclusion et l'internationalisation dans le respect des identités et des minorités, quelles qu'elles soient. La question est de trouver par où entrer dans ce cercle vertueux? Imaginons qu'un début de réponse se trouve dans le projet Papers, dans le Congrès et dans ce Digibook qui le matérialise et représente un premier pas vers l'essaimage. Au commencement, comme à la fin, il y a le partage...

MÉRIEM BEDJAOU
Professeure des Universités
Cheffe du projet Papers, partie Algérienne

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CHAPTER III
INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE INTEGRATION FOR
STUDENTS OF SPANISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE USING ICT

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RÉSUMÉ

L'apprentissage d'une langue étrangère contribue à élargir et à encourager les compétences sociales et interculturelles des apprenants. Parallèlement, la mise en œuvre des technologies de l'information et de la communication (TIC) dans l'enseignement supérieur améliore et résout les problèmes d'apprentissage des étudiants. Ainsi, on pourrait affirmer que l'utilisation des TIC dans l'apprentissage des langues secondes contribue énormément au développement et à l'amélioration de la compétence communicative interculturelle (TIC) pour surmonter les barrières sociales et culturelles des élèves. Les TIC rendent donc l'éducation plus inclusive, individualisée et accessible à divers groupes sociaux.

Cependant, aucune preuve scientifique n'a été fournie quant à la façon dont les activités d'apprentissage en classe pour l'acquisition d'une langue seconde à l'aide de la technologie ont amélioré la compétence communicative interculturelle (CCI) de ces étudiants. Cet article analyse le rôle joué par les ressources TIC dans l'intégration de l'CCI en classe d'espagnol langue seconde. Pour cela, une revue systématique des études a été développée pour décrire comment les TIC sont utilisées pour promouvoir et améliorer l'inclusion sociale par l'intégration de la compétence communicative interculturelle des étudiants espagnols en tant que langue seconde. Les résultats montrent que l'inclusion des TIC semble être bénéfique pour atteindre l'inclusion sociale en classe. Les TIC aident à combler le fossé entre l'apprentissage des langues et l'inclusion sociale et à atteindre l'interculturalité. En outre, les résultats indiquent que l'amélioration des compétences communicatives interculturelles pour les étudiants apprenant l'espagnol en utilisant les TIC est à l'étude et conforme à un nouveau sujet d'intérêt en raison de l'ampleur de l'inclusion culturelle et de la formation des enseignants en Espagne est encore faible.

Mots-clés: CCI, TIC, espagnol en tant que deuxième langue, inclusion sociale.

ABSTRACT

Learning a foreign language contributes to broadening and fostering learners' social and intercultural competencies. At the same time, implementing Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in higher education improves and solves students' learning problems. So, it could be stated that ICT use in second language learning immensely helps developing and enhancing the intercultural communicative competence (ICT) to overcome students' social and cultural barriers. ICT therefore makes education more inclusive, individualized, and accessible to various social groups.

However, no scientific evidence has been provided regarding how learning classroom activities for acquiring a second language using technology have improved intercultural communicative competence (ICC) of these students. This paper analyzes the role played by ICT resources in integrating ICC in Spanish as a Second Language classroom (SL2). For this, a systematic literature investigation review of studies was developed to describe how ICT is being used to promote and improve social inclusion through the incorporation of the intercultural communicative competence of Spanish students as a second language. The results show inclusion of ICT seems to be beneficial for achieving social inclusion in the classroom. ICT helps to bridge the gap between language learning and social inclusion and achieve interculturality. Moreover, the findings indicate that improving intercultural communicative competence for students learning Spanish using ICT is under study and conforms to a new topic of interest due to the scope of culture inclusion and teachers training in Spain is still low.

Keywords: ICC, ICT, Spanish as a second language, social inclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diverse linguistics contexts require different skills to establish social and cultural relations. Therefore, having the intercultural communicative competence (ICC) is vital, and it is only achievable through foreign or second language learning. The inclusion of culture in language classrooms is recommended as it reflects the socio-economic changes. The cultural diversity phenomenon in the Spanish education system comes from the 90's. Societies are becoming more diverse, and Spain is one the most hospitable country of migrants of all types of nationalities with various mother tongues.

Social and cultural inclusion in education will assure a sense of belonging, acceptance, and integration that will allow learners to participate in social, political, and educational activities as "The basic principle of the interactive approach is that the foreign language is learned better through social interaction." (Claros, 2008: 147). Therefore, the urge to acquire a second language is inevitable. Proficiency in the language of the receiving country has been found to play a key role in the migrant-native achievement gap across several studies (Kristen *et al.*, 2011).

Intercultural communicative competence can be defined as possessing the necessary attitudes and reflective behavioral skills and using these to behave effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations (Deardorff, 2006). For their part, Valle *et al.*, (2014) link the ICC with a combination of knowledge and cultural awareness (cognitive component), emotions and attitudes (affective component), and behavior (relational component).

According to Bennett (2009), ICC should be considered the central core and objective of language classrooms rather than the focus of linguistics of a given language. Spanish as a second language (SL2) classrooms are no different. The teachers should have the proper training regarding how to enrich the ICC and, due to the socio-technological context in which are, how to integrate ICT into the learning activities. The technological developments and the emergence of hybrid and electronic learning confers to the teachers' digital competence are more and more relevant. However, educational reformation in Spain has not provided an accurate answer to these training needs for teachers.

This situation underlines that the teacher's readiness to deliver and enhance learners' ICC is critical in teaching a language. This readiness can be achieved and set during the pre-service training or in their work placements but, in any case, must include specific training regarding how to use ICT resources for teaching purposes in multicultural and multilingual contexts. In Spain, these kinds of training are not always joined. The ICC should be the central core and integrate and implement the acquisition of communicative competencies among learners. Besides, our society's technological development requires us to be able to live in a multicultural and digital environment. This emphasizes the merging need of the ICC development of the learners with the acquisition of digital competencies, and the SL2 classroom is an ideal environment for it. The ICT tools foster diverse, multicultural, and multilingual contexts in classrooms where Spanish is taught as a second language to linguistically diverse learners. In this sense, we wonder how teachers are trained to use ICT to improve learners' ICC in the SL2 classrooms and if we have evidence of their results.

2. METHOD

For this paper, we employed a systematic literature review of 16 articles (Table 1) in relation to intercultural communicative, ICT, and Spanish as a second language. Time frame was set from 1998 to 2022. Articles were selected through the Web of Science, ScienceDirect, and Google scholar. Criterias of selection were:

1. The social and cultural inclusion in Spanish education.
2. The integration of ICC in SL2 classrooms.
3. Teachers training in the use of ICT in SL2 classrooms.
4. The results of using ICT in fostering ICC in SL2 classrooms.

N.º	Title	Authors	Year	Journal
1	An Attack on Inclusive Education in Secondary Education. Limitations in Initial Teacher Training in Spain.	Lallana, A., & Salamanca, P.	2020	New Approaches in Educational Research
2	Building Bridges to the Integration of Culture in the EFL Secondary Classroom: Perspectives from Teachers and Learners	Marrón-González, S	2020	Association for Computing Machinery
3	Intercultural communicative competence in L2 Spanish: guidelines for teacher training programmes.	Lallana, A., & Salamanca, P.	2020	Journal of Spanish Language Teaching
4	Distance teaching/learning of foreign languages mediated by information and communication technology tools.	Shiba, K	2020	Xlinguae

N.º	Title	Authors	Year	Journal
5	Teacher beliefs and approaches to linguistic diversity. Spanish as a second language in the inclusion of immigrant students.	Rodríguez-Izquierdo, R., Falcón, I., & Permisán, C.	2020	Teaching and Teacher Education
6	Theories-based Inclusive Education Practices	Al-Shammari, Z., Faulkner, P.E., & Forlin, C.	2019	Education Quarterly Reviews
7	A comparative study of Spanish adult students' attitudes to ICT in classroom, blended and distance language learning modes	Arrosagaray, M., González-Peiteado, M., Pino-Juste, M., & Rodríguez-López, B.	2019	Computers & Education
8	Promoting Social Inclusion in Educational Settings: Challenges and Opportunities.	Juvonen, J., Lessard, L., Rastogi, R., Schacter, H., & Smith, D	2019	Educational Psychologist
9	Promoting social inclusion for migrant populations through media, technologies and languages.	Rico, M., Fielden, L., & Sánchez, H.	2019	The Jalt Call
10	Building Intercultural Competence Through Virtual Team Collaboration Across Global Classrooms.	Swartz, S., Barbosa, B., & Crawford, I.	2019	Business And Professional Communication Quarterly
11	Digital training in intercultural education for teacher training: analysis of an innovative experience.	Díaz, L., Delgado, S., Esteban, P., Tosina, R., & Puerto, G	2018	International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life-Long Learning
12	Intercultural Communicative Competence in Adolescents in Multicultural Contexts.	Valle, R.E., Baelo, R., & López-Rodríguez, E	2014	Diversity in Education
13	Language programs at Villababel High: rethinking ideologies of social inclusion.	Mijares, L., & Relaño, A.	2011	Bilingual Education and Bilingualism

N.º	Title	Authors	Year	Journal
14	Cross cultural reflections on inclusive education.	Barton, L., & Armstrong, F	2008	Policy, Experience and Change
15	Critical approaches to world language education in the United States: an introduction.	Kubota, R., & Austin, T.	2007	Critical Inquiry in Language Studies
16	Using the world wide web to integrate Spanish language and culture: a pilot study.	Osuna, M., & Meskil, C.	1998	Language Learning & Technology

Table 1. Selected articles for review

3. RESULTS

Most of the articles have been published emphasizing the importance of the intercultural communicative competence in foreign language learning and how it is important to integrate culture in classrooms for learners to learn how to communicate effectively with others of different languages (Marrón-González, 2020; Shiba, K, 2020; Lallana & Salamanca, 2020b; Swartz, Barbosa, & Crawford, 2019; Mijares & Relañó Pastor, 2011).

However, little research related to Spanish as a second language teaching and learning, some authors found out that culture had not been featured in previous L2 learning experiences, for some is related to the lack of teachers training (Lallana & Salamanca, 2020a). This was another important element discussed in most of the articles, it is a crucial part in assuring an effective learner with skilled intercultural communicative competence, teachers find it hard to design courses with activities and resources that target the ICC of the learners. Since there is no manual nor a guide to follow, teachers find themselves to be autonomous in using ICT tools such as the use of authentic materials, intercultural models (i.e., Byram's model 1977) to integrate culture in the classroom.

This autonomous integration of ICC in language classrooms using ICT did not indicate whether there are effective results especially, in terms of SL2. Nonetheless, the articles selected indicate that with the development in technology and the widespread use of electronic devices among people, it can be assured that its use can be effective but only if it is done in the right way.

4. DISCUSSION

According to the articles and the review being conducted, Spain has a long way to go in terms of including all students of all kinds of special needs, whether diagnosed or not. Several authors stated that teachers need to be interculturally competent themselves (Sercu *et al.* 2005, Dimitrov & Haque 2016). Despite the diversity of languages and cultures in Spain, it has never been the interest, since the segregation in 1980 of policymakers

and educators, to establish a curriculum that reflects the society by integrating culture and improving the ICC through resources such as ICT. This results in a general lack of training in the use of ICT and on how to use it to gain ICC in SL2 classrooms. The lack of training and policies in this field cause teachers to take measures and design activities autonomously to help students foster their intercultural communicative competence. Although no results are shown on the success of the use of ICT in improving ICC, most teachers are still integrating ICT in their SL2 teaching. Finally, based on our systematic literature review, there are few shreds of evidence related to integrating ICC in SL2 classrooms using ICT, this lack of proof made it hard for us to provide proper arguments and discussion regarding ICT in SL2 classrooms.

5. CONCLUSION

Intercultural communicative competence integration in language classrooms is a way of looking at these contents outside the box, putting out of focus the merely linguistic aspects. With the growth of migrants in Spain, the language demands and requirements changed, learners of SL2 find themselves in need of mastering the Spanish language as a way to enhance their integration into society. Schools and education, in general, took a leap to incorporate the ICC in foreign or second language learning and teaching. However, no showcase on how to do so despite the availability of ICT resources to use to foster learners' ICC and cultural skills, no training is being provided for them. Spain has a long way to go in preparing teachers for learning in multicultural teaching contexts.

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